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Immigration, Remittances and Rural Development: A Case Study of Balasore District in Odisha

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ABSTRACT

In the rural area or household, remittances are quite vital in enhancing the life of the people economically. In Indian rural households, remittances are received by the family members from the internal migrants comprising of skilled, semiskilled and unskilled workers and white collared professionals working in different parts of India as well as from the Indian immigrants or diaspora living in different parts of the globe. India stands at the top in the world in terms of receiving foreign remittances. Remittances have been a very significant source of economic development and philanthropic activities. Remittances are used in meeting the food, health, education and other essential expenditure of the migrants' family members. Remittances stimulate economic development and generate economic activities in the area of origin of the migrants. Remittances are also used for the village development and many philanthropic activities including building of schools, hospitals, libraries, parks, roads etc. The paper tries to study the impact of remittances especially sent by the immigrant workers residing in different parts of the world on the rural economic development and philanthropy focussing on the immigrants from selected areas of Balasore district in Odisha.

Keyword: Immigration, Remittances, Rural Development, Philanthropy

INTRODUCTION

Migration is defined as a crossing of geographical space. Migration can be internal as well as international. International migration of Indians, widely known as the diaspora, generally refers to the emigration of people to foreign lands (Naujoks,2009). The money that diaspora members earn and save are sent to their home countries on a regular basis in the form of remittances. Remittances from migrants have become crucial in development studies during the last two decades. With increasing international and internal migration, they are considered to be an "important and stable source of external

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development finance” for households in their source regions (Ratha, 2003), reducing transient poverty and, at times, structural poverty (Kapur, 2004; Quoted by Tumba, 2011). At the same time, remittances can lead to financial dependence, divert attention away from productive investments, and increase inequality in source regions due to the self-selection nature of migration (imf.org and Ratha, 2020).

In the beginning, remittance was primarily considered in terms of money. Over time, the concept of remittances became more expansive, and researchers began to pay more attention to the remittance patterns. Among the researchers who studied social remittances is Peggy Levitt. She had conducted research in the Dominican Republic and watched immigrants in the United States. Diaspora members who return to their home nations carry with them not just financial resources, but also the cultural and intellectual capital they have gained while living and working in the host country, as well as the knowledge and experience they have gained in the process (Peggy Levitt & Lamba-Nieves, 2011). Diaspora members adapt to their new country’s culture, work and live among different nationalities, and bring these traits back to their home country which are more important than money sent by diaspora members to their native country of origin, according to Peggy Levitt and Lamba (Peggy Levitt & Lamba-Nieves, 2011). According to Levitt and others, the four forms of social remittances that immigrants and members of the diaspora send back to their home countries are practises, social capital, identities, and norms (Peggy Levitt & Lamba-Nieves, 2011). Apart from remittances people from diaspora transmit skill and expertise, which they propagate when they return home. The remittances are used for a variety of purposes and are sent via the correct channels.

Remittances are one of the prime revenue sources for several nations, and the large chunk of their GDP comes from remittances. They are crucial for the growth of those nations. In 2024 alone, remittance inflows to India reached an estimated \$129 billion (Ratha et al., 2025). For the past two decades, India has succeeded in maintaining its top position in so far as receiving of remittances is concerned. During the period of crisis remittances have been quite handy in addressing the economic challenges. Remittances from migrants significantly augmented the effectiveness of government cash transfer programmes to assist families experiencing economic challenges during the Covid-19 crisis (Asian Development Bank et al., 2020). Remittance money has

greatly supplemented govt’s initiatives in dealing with the economic challenges during covid-19 (Ratha et al., 2025). The flow of remittances to assist households with stretched finances should be a significant component of government initiatives to enable a worldwide recovery from the pandemic (Rutkowski M. et al., 2021).

The paper discusses the importance of remittances in addressing the household expenses and generating economic activities in the locality. It also analyses the shifting dynamics of remittances and assesses the value of remittances to national economic concerns. It tries to find out the influence that remittances have on the immigrant families in Balasore district of Odisha analysing various sources and utilization of remittances sent back home by immigrants.

The principal income source for immigrant households in the selected villages of Balasore district of Odisha under study was money sent back home by immigrants. At the time of the field study, immigrants’ households were receiving remittances. The study also covered the method of sending remittances that immigrants employed. It also analysed the frequency of the transfer through official and informal channels studying if there had been any variations in frequency throughout the period. Another important fact is that remittances lead to the socio-economic wellbeing of households, including the elimination of credit constraints, the lifting of families from the economic status they were prior to the immigration of their members, and the accessibility of better schooling or education and better healthcare for the households.

The village demographics and socio-economic characteristics of the immigrants, which includes information such as the path they took to migrate, the countries they resided in before to leaving, and the employment they held once they arrived in their new nations of residence etc. are examined in the study. As per the field study, considering the education level of the immigrants, maximum number of immigrants were having degrees in technical education, which is the highest number in so far as selected immigrants are concerned. It was found that the majority of immigrants worked in the professional sector either with a technical degree or in low-skilled employment like driving. A total of 46.7% of the immigrants are employed in professional positions such as CA, doctors, engineers, and educators, compared to a mean of 6.7% in the skilled worker sector and 10.0 percent in the clerical sector. Educators, professors, and lecturers make up a significant portion of the immigrant population, at around 13.3%.

OBJECTIVES

The paper makes an attempt to study the utilisation patterns of the remittances by the immigrant households and the remittance induced economic activities improving the economic status of the family and contributing to village development.

METHODOLOGY

This research study uses both qualitative and quantitative tools. A detailed questionnaire was prepared containing the demographic details, remittance sending patterns, use of remittances by the households, contribution of remittances to local economic development and philanthropic activities carried out by the immigrants. The total sample size of the study is 30. Random sampling method was used for finding out the respondents. The field study was conducted in the selected areas like, Balasore Town, Balasore Sadar, Basta, Baliapal, Chandipur, Jaleswar, Bhograi, Khaira, Remuna, Soro, Bahanaga, Nilagiri, and Rupsa in Balasore district of Odisha. SPSS was used for categorisation and analysis of data.

IMMIGRANTS AND THEIR FAMILIES

Out of the total number of households of the immigrants under study 40.0 percent are found to be nuclear families, 50.0% are found to be joint families, and the remaining 10.0 percent are found to be extended families respectively. From the study it is found that an overall 80.0% of the households resided in pucca houses, while 20% of the families lived in bungalow type houses. None of the households lived in kucha houses. This is indicative of the fact that more amount of money are spent by families on the construction of houses. It is obvious that the building or renovation of these residences resulted in the generation of employment prospects for local workers. The construction or renovation of those houses is typically performed by individuals who either belong to the village or from the nearby villages.

REASONS OF MIGRATION

One of the most critical elements in each immigration research has been the motivation for the migration. Migration may be better understood by looking at the push-pull forces. Apart from the conventional causes for migration, this research has taken into account other factors that are specific to the studied region.

Source: Author's estimation of primary data

However, from the data collected from the field most of the immigrants are largely driven by 'financial issues,' according to the findings it is 40 percent. However, 'greater economic prospects' are cited as the second most important reason, accounting for 33.3%. 20.0 percent of the people moved abroad (primarily to the United States) because they wanted to get better education. 3.3 percent of the immigrants had relocated to other countries 'with spouse.' 3.3 percent of the

immigrants stayed back in the host countries after completing their study.

MODES OF TRANSFER OF REMITTANCES

In the digital era, the old ways of sending money through friends, relatives or postal money orders have largely given way to modern banking systems and digitalisation platforms. This transformation has made remittances faster, safer and more reliable to migrant

communities to support their families as well as the villages. Broadly remittance transfer flows for two purposes, one is to economically support immigrant households and another for philanthropic purpose.

Mode of Sending Remittances to Immigrant Household

Mode of Sending Remittances to Immigrant Household	Percent (%)
Direct Transfer (Online Banking) to Family Accounts	95.0
MTO (Money Transfer Operators)	5.0
Total	100.0

Source: Author’s estimation of primary data

As per the mean field study data given above on mode of sending remittances to the household of immigrants, it is found that 95% of remittances are sent directly to the accounts of family members of immigrants through online banking.

The immigrants from the Balasore district of Odisha have faith in numerous village/town bodies/trusts that care and look after social problems in the countryside. Diaspora members pay remittances on a regular basis, which are used for projects in villages such as planting trees, beautifying towns, sanitation, caring for the cow shelter, maintaining village ponds etc.

Mode of Transfer of Remittances to the Village/Town Bodies for Philanthropic Purposes

Mode of Transfer of Remittances to the Village/Town Bodies for Philanthropic Purposes	Percentage
Direct transfer (online banking/ remittances services) to village account	60.0
Direct transfer to other immigrant/NRI friends’ bank account from other village	10.0
Direct transfer to Bank Account of Village Samiti	6.7
Post office /Money order	3.3
Relatives	6.7
Friends	3.3
MTO (money transfer operators)	10.0
Total	100.0

Source: Author’s estimation of primary data

In the study it has been seen that remittance transmission modalities are an important aspect of any remittance analysis. In the study, in so far as sending of remittances for philanthropic purposes are concerned, the majority (60.0 percent) of remittances were transferred directly to the village bank accounts, and 10.0 percent of the remittances were transferred to the bank accounts of immigrant/NRI friends of the immigrants mostly from other villages. A substantial 6.7 percent were transferred directly to the bank account of village samiti. In this survey, it was also observed that MTOs (10.0 percent) and post office or money order are used by a smaller number of immigrants to send money (3.3 percent).

However, it should be noted that remittances from informal sources are received by a considerable majority of the total families. This suggests that, although informal channels of transfer are less common than official ones, they do exist, such as the hawala or hundi networks. It is necessary to emphasise in this regard that the cost of transfer and the time needed for transfer play a determining role in the choice of channels that is made by the immigrants (RBI, 2009; Singh, 2010). In addition, the level of financial literacy possessed by immigrants, in addition to that of the family members in their origin countries, may also be a key influence in deciding which channels are used.

USE OF REMITTANCES BY THE HOUSEHOLDS

The topics covered include the length of time that immigrant households have been receiving remittances; the number of times that remittances are received annually; the currency in which remittances are received; the purpose for which remittances are sent; the primary recipient of remittances; and whether or not there have been any changes in the size or frequency of remittance receipts. Along with the length of time that remittances are received, the frequency with which they are received and the regularity with which immigrant families get money sent back home are also essential factors in determining the effect of remittances. Out of mean samples 26.7 percent received remittances monthly and 6.7 percent received them irregularly, that is, it varied between years and could be twice a year

(20.0 percent), once a year (30.0 percent), or annually depending on the immigrant’s financial situation at the destination.

By studying the economic obligation of the households, the study was trying to find out the answers on spending by the households as per their urgency.

Source: Author’s estimation of primary data

Respondents were asked about their financial obligations, including payments on a vehicle loan (33.3 percent), house loan (23.3 percent), supporting other relatives financially (10.0 percent), contributions to social security premiums (10.0 percent), donations given for community services (10.0 percent), and payments for loans taken for meeting the travelling cost to go abroad (6.7 percent). Family debt repayment for vehicle loans is the most significant source of financial stress (almost 33.3 percent).

The reason for sending remittances is also an essential variable that allows us to identify the primary reasons why remittances are needed in families and so constitutes an important driver of remittance size. In the survey, respondents were questioned about the precise multi-response reasons why migrants would contribute money to homes. Below table and figure depict the many objectives for which migrants transferred money to homes, in order of significance, as indicated by respondents.

Source: Author’s estimation of primary data

M1: Most Important, 1M1: First Most Important, 2M1: Second Most Important, 3M1: Third Most Important, 4M1: Fourth Most Important

PURPOSES	PERCENTAGE				
	MI	1MI	2MI	3MI	4MI
Basic minimum needs of family	60.0(18)	36.7(11)	3.3(1)	00.0	00.0
Medical needs of the family	40.0(12)	53.3(16)	6.7(2)	0.00(0)	00.0(0)
Loan repayment	3.3(1)	6.7(2)	23.3(7)	30.0(9)	36.7(11)
Schooling of children	0.00(0)	3.3(1)	40.0(12)	23.3(7)	33.3(10)
Other purpose	0.00(0)	0.00(0)	26.7(8)	46.7(14)	26.7(8)

The most important reason for sending money was to meet the basic minimum needs of the family, such as food and other daily requirements (60.0%), followed by medical needs of the family (40%) and loan payment (3.3%), as selected by households with varying opinions.

However, when it comes to families sending remittances for other purposes, investments in land, business ventures, etc. are hardly mentioned. Repayment of loans,

medical expenses, and investment remained equally major reasons for sending remittances by immigrants.

The information shown in the graph demonstrates the proportion of immigrant families who utilised money from remittances to particularly construct new dwellings, remodel or renovate existing houses, and acquire commodities. It also states the philanthropic activities undertaken by the immigrants.

Source: Author's estimation of primary data

It can be observed from this graph that a substantial 23.3 percent of immigrant families in the villages of Balasore district utilised remittance money towards the construction of new dwellings, and that 20 percent of households also spent money on improving/renovating their current homes. It is obvious that this results in the creation of job opportunities in the locality. The remittance money was utilised by certain members of immigrant families to establish microenterprises or to

invest in commercial operations. Also, a sizeable percentage of immigrant households in the villages, used the money from their remittances to buy long-lasting and other goods that are not available in the village. This led to the generation of some trade activities in the villages, as residents stated that some retail businesses are established in the village to satisfy the requirements of the villagers and the immigrant households are the regular buyers and their purchasing was more. It was

observed that in the selected villages of Balasore district many immigrant households employed labour from their own households for domestic work.

The researcher noticed through the responses of the respondents that the remittances sent back by immigrant households generate employment opportunities for local people in the village. These employment opportunities can be found in the construction industry, in business and microenterprises, and in trade with the surrounding area.

It is the ability of the household to earn additional money by investing remittance money. Remittances have enormous contribution on the creation of asset particularly the ownership of lands in the home countries of migrants. Families of migrants who had agricultural land also tended to invest the remittances in the creation of land asset. That demonstrated that remittances and migration from rural to urban areas served investment as well as consumption purposes (Tumbe, 2016). According to another study conducted in Botswana revealed that remittances are often invested in fixed capital, such as lands, cattle, or homes (International Trade Administration, 2025). Respondents under study were found investing in microenterprises of the locality such as ice factory, prawn farming etc.

IMPACT OF REMITTANCES ON VILLAGE DEVELOPMENT

Money sent by immigrants to their home countries are indicative of the economic importance of immigrants. The influence of remittances on homeland development would depend on the reason for the transfer of remittances. Remittances can have an impact on macroeconomic and microeconomic research. In terms of macroeconomics, remittances: 1) help receiving families prosper and provide temporary emergency funds; 2) tend to increase during times of economic crisis and natural disasters; 3) raise living standards through human and capital investment (health, nutrition, and education) and asset building (such as real estate, business, and saving); and 4) have effects on families and society outside of the receiving families, among other things (Hidayati, 2018). Remittances are a reliable source of cash, a vital supply of foreign exchange for the nation, and a solution to the pressure on the value of the currency in terms of macroeconomics (Hidayati, 2018).

Based on the research on the overall development scenario of the villages, it is found that there was a lot of variation in the development pattern

of the villages with regard to the most fundamental facilities, schools, and educational opportunities, as well as medical care services. The community derives the majority of its revenue from agriculture and fisheries production, with less developed processing industries. The village's efforts to improve themselves do not have adequate funding to support them. The contributions by the immigrants have greatly facilitated the community development activities.

The village's social and economic improvements are made better due to the remittances. The improvements can be marked in the living conditions of the households and the developments in the locality. Even if they were physically separated, remittances were immigrants' attempt to continue their socio-economic ties with their home nations. NRIS along with the immigrant population have contributed for the building of various colleges. It is observed that some urban as well as rural area colleges are founded or collaborated with NRIS or immigrants. It's worth noting that the villages' immigrant populations have been actively participating in a number of community development initiatives. Some Gulf immigrants have donated land to the panchayat for an animal hospital and a local Muslim association with Gulf connections has funded orphanages in the village. The Gulf connections and the NRI community's collective remittances have contributed a lot for the development of both non-immigrant households and their village community in the areas selected for the study. Immigrant families also gave money to orphanages, temples, churches, gurudwaras, and mosques.

It was found that the remittances sent back by immigrant families influenced the non-immigrant households in various ways, such as via charitable contributions. This was yet another fascinating aspect of the data. During rituals, particularly weddings and funerals, it was found that immigrant families in villages give money to some of their non-immigrant relatives living in the villages. There was an act of philanthropy that took place in the form of financial support or certain helps by the immigrants/immigrant households in the form of giving jewellery, items, goods etc., for the weddings and other celebrations of their non-immigrant relatives.

The diaspora's philanthropically driven efforts are studied and examined. Diaspora philanthropy focuses on reducing poverty, delivering social justice in the form of universal healthcare, universal education,

a clean environment for people and animals to live in, human security, particularly for disadvantaged populations, and the enjoyment of human rights. The Odia diaspora's charity activities are studied via interviews with local people of communities.

There are several places in the Municipality and nearby Gram Panchayat where social remittances have played an important role in creating various philanthropic work. Some works carried out by these remittances are in the form of a well-established public library, clean roads, water supply for the whole town, a well-maintained public park, and schools, all of which have been benefited significantly by the remittances from Odia immigrants. During the field visit of this research work, the researcher found out that several communities are the cleanest in the area.

Religious people tend to give generously to charity. Religious groups across the globe generate money to support their programmes and initiatives. To organise various religious programmes and functions, there is a need for financial support. Every state in India has a big number of immigrant groups who support religious festivals and activities. Lord Venkateshwara at Tirupathi, South India, receives contributions from both overseas Indians and foreigners. Hindu diaspora members generously contribute to ISKON, Jagannath Temple etc. Similarly other religious communities contribute to the building of mosques, churches, gurudwaras etc. and provide financial support to various programmes and festivals.

Members of the Odia diaspora community residing in different countries, particularly in USA, Australia, UK, and Canada etc. have built temples dedicated to God Jagannath. They have been donating money for the building of new temples and the rehabilitation of existing and damaged temples in Balasore. From the field survey it is known that a diaspora member regularly visits Baba Bhusandeswar Shiv Mandir in Balasore. The Mandir is open to the public free of charge, a sign that the religious remittances sent back to Odisha by the Odia diaspora have been put to productive use.

CONCLUSION

Remittances, immigration, and national growth are all interconnected. Remittances contribute for village development. Majority of people reside in rural areas in emerging nations, and poverty rates are strongly

correlated with the location of these populations. Most people in rural villages are subsistence farmers, making it difficult to escape poverty. Diaspora remittances to India significantly improve rural income, and these rural people are more likely to spend since money is readily available from family and friends in the Indian diaspora (Azad, Nirmal S. and Amandeep Kaur, 2004). Other options for increasing village revenue exist. Adopting modern technology in agriculture is one such option, and using diaspora funds, machinery required for agricultural labour in rural regions may be purchased. The development of non-agricultural work may also be impacted by remittances from the diaspora.

As crucial components in the migration process remittances cannot be dissociated. Remittances are another good that migrants produce, and their families in their home countries anxiously await them. Remittances, however, are not only welcomed by the families of migrants, but they also benefit their home countries. Remittance is therefore a process of migration that is transmitted to the homeland in both tangible (such as commodities or money) and immaterial (such as the improvement of skills and developmental ideas that have advantages for the homeland of migrants) forms (Hidayati, 2018). Remittances have indeed been contributing to the rural development improving the economic life of the rural people.

From the result of the household survey and the interviews taken from the Sarpanch, Ward members and other people of the respondents' villages in Balasore, it was found that fairly a substantial number of immigrant households in Balasore are involved in donation for plantation, innovation, schools, colleges, schools for blind people and some projects like, mineral drinking water plant etc. which symbolises the development of villages in the study area. The study further finds that each family pays money to the community development project. These individual contributions from houses make a significant contribution to the overall welfare of the community in the village. The self-sufficiency of the village, which includes the provision of fundamental utilities such as a well-paved road, power and water supply, and municipal amenities like, schools and hospitals can be ascribed to the initiatives and contributions made by the community's immigrants. Undoubtedly, remittances play a very pivotal role in the rural development as has been found out in the field study conducted in the Balasore district of Odisha.

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The authors declare no competing interests.

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